

University of Nebraska - Lincoln

DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln

Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

Libraries at University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Winter 1-16-2022

Evaluation of Library Services and Facilities by the Students of BLDE (DU) during the Pandemic COVID-19: A Study

Prasanna Kumara BM

BLDE (Deemed to be University), Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura, prasannamlib23@gmail.com

Shivakumar Acharya

BLDE (Deemed to be University), Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura, shivakumar.15august@gmail.com

Follow this and additional works at: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac>

Part of the [Health Sciences and Medical Librarianship Commons](#), and the [Scholarly Communication Commons](#)

Kumara BM, Prasanna and Acharya, Shivakumar, "Evaluation of Library Services and Facilities by the Students of BLDE (DU) during the Pandemic COVID-19: A Study" (2022). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 6847.

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6847>

Evaluation of Library Services and Facilities by the Students of BLDE (DU) during the Pandemic COVID-19: A Study

Shivakumar Acharya¹, Prasanna Kumara B.M. (Corresponding)²

Abstract

The library plays a significant role in any higher education centre to that provides formation services, resources, and facilities to support its clients for their systematic studies and research activities. This study deals with the awareness and usage of various services and facilities offered by the BLDE (DU) central library during the Pandemic. The research method adopted for this study was a Google Form with a self-designed questionnaire was prepared and circulated randomly among 100 PG students of BLDE-DU, in which 66 were responded. The result revealed that almost all the postgraduate students who responded are aware of the central library's variety of services & facilities. Circulation service is the major service that the PG students utilized following Plagiarism check and Literature search services. The research proposes that user satisfaction assessments be promoted based on the study's results. In addition, library administration should provide training sessions on how to utilise library services effectively on a regular basis. This research adds to the body of knowledge, policy, and practise, especially when it comes to accessing library services and facilities during pandemics like COVID-19.

Keywords: *Library Services, Library Facilities, Library Usage, Information Seeking Behavior, University Library, Covid-19*

1. Assistant Librarian, BLDE (Deemed to be University)-Vijayapura- <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6347-9213>, 2. University Librarian, BLDE (Deemed to be University)- Vijayapura- <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2760-443X>

Introduction

Governments throughout the world have imposed complete or partial lockdowns to curb the spread of the COVID-19 outbreak. However, these lockdowns had serious economic and social consequences, posing unique challenges in the educational sector, forcing not only students, but also policymakers and service providers, such as librarians, to adapt and adopt technology as a viable and valuable option for meeting stakeholders' educational needs and overcoming a variety of obstacles. Furthermore, as a preventive step to prevent the virus from spreading further, the Indian government announced the closure of all educational institutions throughout the nation on March 16, 2020, for a period of fifteen days (Times of India, 2020).

The school education sector moved quicker than the higher education sector in India to convert its whole operation to an online platform in response to the countrywide shutdown in March and April 2020. (Wadia, 2020). One of the reasons for this may be the time and length of the original decision to shut educational institutions in India. According to most higher education institutions' academic calendars, classroom instruction was almost complete, and exams were about to begin. However, because of the Pandemic's fast-developing circumstances, the University Grants Commission (UGC), India's top authority for higher education, decided to postpone all exams save the terminal semester/final years and ordered that they be completed by the end of September 2020. (University Grants Commission, 2020). Due to the suspension of in-person services and the loss of Access to physical collections at the schools' libraries, students, professors, and library professionals consider embracing technology as the only option to

weather the storm. During the lockdown, library staff showed their abilities, sensitivity, and flexibility in responding to quickly changing circumstances. In such cases, the website becomes a vital and dynamic platform for connecting with and serving the targeted consumers. However, technology alone will not be sufficient. In this unusual and urgent circumstance, library professionals, particularly those from leading health institutions, play a critical role in informing their customers about the facilities and services that they provide.

The library has held a vital position since the middle of March 2020, a time when it has been uniquely situated to act as a key building. The library is open to BLDE(DU) faculty, students, and staff, but not to community users; the building is accessible with only one door open, while all three other entrances are locked; the first floor is open to BLDE(DU) faculty, students, and staff, but not to community users; the library is open to BLDE(DU) faculty, students, and staff, but not to community users; and the majority of library staff work from home, with the exception of the University Librarian and about four. Many other services, on the other hand, have been switched to totally online intervention.

Literature Review

Weeks A, Houk KM, Nugent RL, Corn M, Lackey M. say that Cooperation between a few College of Medicine offices, including the library, brought about another help for personnel during the COVID-19 pandemic emergency. By consolidating endeavors, uphold for instructing on the web turned into an assembled exertion and significantly less overwhelming for the workforce, which could counsel one gathering for web-based showing support, as opposed to three or four unique elements. The subsequent undertaking prompted a site FAQ and counselling email address open to all workforces to give engaged and ideal innovation and instruction help to staff.

Cote MP, Donne EM, Hoover BD, Thormodson K. study shows institutional archives are essential in clinical schools and scholastic wellbeing communities, and just a few wellbeing frameworks have utilized them to follow and advance their examination and academic action. This article depicts how Providence System Library Services utilized their current institutional store stage to substitute a virtual feature for a yearly in-person occasion.

Martin HJ, Schwartz A. The role of health science administrators in the Covid Pandemic is investigated by say ordinary Element. COVID19 has swiftly spread over the globe. All major metropolitan areas throughout the globe have been placed under lockdown. In Pakistan, the first case was evaluated on February 26, 2020, and as of March 31, 2020, there were more than 2039 assessed cases and 26 fatalities. There are another 12 000 suspected cases around the country. If no precautions are taken, this will undoubtedly increase. Pakistan's universities, colleges, and schools were all shut down. College curators' roles in this crisis included bringing concerns to light via general health education, assisting clinical professionals and scientists, and providing ongoing traditional sorts of aid to regular library patrons in Pakistan. The Standard Component also contributes to valued assets.

In their Study, Ali MY, Gatiti P. explain that the COVID-19 Pandemic has presented huge difficulties for wellbeing science custodians. During this Pandemic, curators are assuming a functioning part by expanding the public's attention to the infection, keeping up archive conveyance benefits and giving examination uphold. This paper utilizes the strategy for work area examination of the sites of chosen library relationship to distinguish the reactions of wellbeing science custodians to the COVID-19 Pandemic. The investigation features huge activities taken by some wellbeing science administrators which others can recreate to address the issues of library clients in the COVID-19 wellbeing emergency.

Statement of the Problem

It is found that there is an issue of underutilization of services, facilities and resources. It has been found that regardless of the university library's huge budget used to get different facilities, resources, and services, there is helpless clients' support in the library administrations. Distinguishing the purposes behind vulnerable support will empower the library to learn the strength and shortcomings of services delivered to clients. This will help library administrators find answers for the issues recognized.

Therefore, this study seeks to investigate reasons for postgraduate students' low usage of library services, looking at " Evaluation of Library Services and Facilities by the Students of BLDE (DU) during the pandemic COVID-19: A Study."

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the usage and awareness of services and facilities available in the Central Library of BLDE (DU).
- Investigate the frequency of use of the library services by postgraduates' students in BLDE (DU).
- Investigate challenges the postgraduates' students face when utilizing the library services in BLDE (DU).
- To get the suggestions for improving services & facilities available in the Central Library of BLDE (DU).

Scope and Methodology

During the COVID-19 epidemic, the current research seeks to explain the library's different services that are utilized to satisfy the requirements of its end-users. The writers' personal experiences working in an academic library, observations of the library's reactions to its resources and services, and thoughts on what might be considered for growth now and in the future are all utilized as methods. For this study, a Google Form containing a self-designed questionnaire was created and distributed randomly to 100 PG students at BLDE (DU), with 66 students responding.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Gender wise distribution

Table-1: Gender wise distribution

Sex	Respondents	Percentage
Male	23	35%
Female	43	65%
Total	66	100%

Table-1 depicts that the number of male respondents is 23 representing 35% of the respondents, while female respondents are 43, representing 65% of the total respondents.

Department wise distribution

Table-2: Department wise distribution

Department	Respondents	Percentage
Anesthesiology	10	15.15
Biochemistry	1	1.52
Community medicine	1	1.52
Dermatology	4	6.06
ENT	2	3.03
General Medicine	11	16.67
General Surgery	10	15.15
OBG	3	4.54
Ophthalmology	4	6.06
Orthopaedics	3	4.54
Pathology	11	16.67
Paediatrics	3	4.54
Radiology	2	3.03
Urology	1	1.52
Total	66	100%

Table-2 clearly explains that most respondents are from General Medicine and Pathology (33.34%). The least respondent departments are Biochemistry, Community Medicine, and Urology, showing 4.56% with one respondent from the department.

Frequency of visit

Table-3: Frequency of visit

Frequency of visit	Response	Chi-square Value	P-value
Frequently (3 or more times a week)	19	27.515	0.001
Never	5		
Occasionally (5 to 9 times a module)	35		
Seldom (4 or less times a year)	7		
Grand Total	66		

The above table-3 clearly shows that 53% of respondents visited the Central library occasionally during the Pandemic, whereas only 7% of the respondents had seldom visited the Central Library. This depicts that more students utilized the Central library for their information need.

Time spent the library kept open during the Pandemic COVID-19

Table-4: Time spent the library kept open during the pandemic COVID-19.

Hours	Respondents	Percentage
Less than 30 Min.	2	3%
1- 2 hrs.	3	4%
3 -4 hrs.	6	9%
4- 5 hrs.	38	58%
More than 6 hrs.	17	26%
	66	100%

Table-4 shows that During the Pandemic period (March-December 2020), the central library was daily kept open 13 hrs. The majority of the respondents, 38 (58 %) spent 4 to 5 hours in the library and 2(3%) of respondents spent the less than 30 mint in a day.

Utilization of Library Services

Table- 5 Utilization of Library Services

Library Services	Response	%	Rank
Circulation of books/journals	62	93.9	1
Plagiarism check	53	80.3	2
Literature Search through database and internet resources	40	60.6	3
Library Orientation	40	60.6	4
OPAC (Online Public Access Catalog)	37	56.1	5
Remote AccessAccess to library resources	36	54.5	6
Departmental Library Service	32	48.5	7
Document Delivery Service (DDS) (journal article book, videos, ppt etc.)	30	45.5	8
Email / SMS Alert Service	29	43.9	9
Reprographic Service	28	42.4	10
User feedback about Central Library through QR code	27	40.9	11
Current Awareness Services (CAS)	26	39.4	12
Newspapers clipping Service	15	22.7	13
Reference citation	10	15.2	14
Assisting in the selection of a journal for publication.	9	7.6	15
Compilation of bibliography on request (list of books, journals subject-wise)	7	10.6	16
Indexing Service	4	6.1	17
Book bank service for SC/ST students	4	6.1	17

The responses summarized in Table 5 were about how the students have offered and utilized the library services during the Pandemic. These answers show the diversity of library services and the wide range of objectives. It depicts that the Circulation service is the most frequently utilized service with 62 respondents (93.9%) followed by a Plagiarism check (80.3%), Library orientation (60.6%). Indexing and Book Bank Services were the least utilized services comprising of 6.1% each.

Precautions taken by the Central Library during the Pandemic.

Figure – 1: Precautions are taken by the Central Library during the Pandemic

The Figure1 clearly shows that the precaution-Maintenance of Social Distancing is the most known and utilized precaution with 89.4% response followed by Wearing of mask-86.4%, use of sanitizer (83.3%) and Hot drinking water facility (60.6%). The Temperature check precaution was the least known and utilized precaution with 19.7%.

Use of Remote Access

Table-6: Use of Remote Access

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	54	82%
No	12	18%
Total	66	100%

We can easily conclude the above table-6 that 54 respondents, i.e., 82% of respondents, used their Remote Access credentials to connect to the Central Library online resources when they were physically far away during the Pandemic.

Resources accessed through the remote Access

Figure2: Resources accessed through the remote Access

The Figure No.2 reveals that the PubMed database is the most widely utilized resource/database with 78.8% responses, followed by the Institutional Repository database (D-Space) with 68.2% and OPAC with 50% responses.

Challenges of the Library Services during the pandemic Covid - 19

Figure3: Challenges of the Library Services during the pandemic Covid - 19

From the above Figure3 anybody can depict that Information of new arrivals was the most significant challenge faced by the respondents with 34.8% response followed by Not up-to-date Information with 28.8% response. It also shows that the Central Library staff were very co-operating during the Pandemic with 0% response to the challenge faced.

Table-7: Satisfaction of Library Services & Facilities during this Pandemic?

Library Services & Facilities	Excellent	Very Good	Satisfactory	Average
Library Services	26	33	6	1
Library Facilities	13	40	11	2
Library Staff cooperation	15	44	6	1
Library timing hours	10	35	12	9
Library environment	15	40	10	1
Library Precautions for Pandemic	12	31	17	6

Figure4: Satisfaction of Library Services & Facilities

Table-7 and Figure 4 clearly shows that almost 98% of the respondents were satisfied with the services provided by the Central library during the Pandemic period, and only 2% of respondents were not satisfied to their extent hence they responded that the services were average. Also shows that 97% (i.e., 64 respondents) were satisfied with the facilities offered by the Central Library in different levels whereas only 3% (i.e., 2 respondents) were not satisfied to their extent. Self explains that 99% (i.e., 65) respondents were satisfied with the Cooperation given by the Central Library staff during the Pandemic. In contrast, only one respondent responded the Cooperation given by the Central Library staff during the Pandemic was average. During the Pandemic period, the central library was daily kept open 13 hrs. (i.e., 08.00 am to 09.00 pm.). 86% of the respondents were happy in different levels, whereas only nine respondents (i.e., 14%) were not satisfied with the library timing hours.

Conclusion

It was uncovered that the postgraduate students know about different services delivered in the university library. Borrowing library materials is the most disparaged service, and the clientele also utilizes similarity check very well. The serious issues confronting the clients in utilizing library facilities and services are the absence of current books and periodicals. Likewise, unsteady force supply is additionally distinguished. Based on the discoveries of the examination, the accompanying proposals are made. There is a need for library authorities to buy in current books and periodicals. The alternative power supply should be given, for example, sun-oriented energy.

Furthermore, the library climate should help utilize library services. A satisfactory arrangement ought to be made for air conditioner. An adequate overview of the client's fulfilment ought to be completed to decide the estimation of administrations and the region that needs improvement. The library authority ought to coordinate library programs that will make attention to clients on different services that have been rendered in the library. This will help with advancing the picture of the library.

Consequently, clients will know about different advantages from utilizing the library facilities and services. The short come of the investigation laid on the way that it is a pilot investigation thus the respondents were very few. Furthermore, the investigation is restricted to the PGs at the university BLDE (DU); subsequently, the discoveries may not be summed up. There is a requirement for examining the awareness and utilization of library resources among undergraduate, Ph. D and staff in the different universities in the country. The inference of this investigation is that it gives new Information to the library administrators on the perception and utilization of library resources by the postgraduates. Moreover, the investigation will be valuable for strategy producers in the library, adding to writing.

References:

1. International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). Key Resources for Libraries in responding to the Coronavirus Pandemic COVID-19 and the Global Library Field. COVID-19 Glob Libr F [Internet]. 2020;1–17. Available from: <https://www.ifla.org/covid-19-and-libraries#reopening>
2. Falt, Eric and Das P. Covid-19 put brake to academic activity, but digital libraries can

ensure continuity. *The Print*. 2020;1–5.

3. Ilori ME. A Pilot Study on awareness and use Library Services among Postgraduate Students in Nigeria. *Libr Philos Pract*. 2019;2019.

4. Reclaims M, Loan I, Delivery D, Prints P. FAQ – Library Services during the Corona Pandemic. 2020;1–2.

5. Settings UC. Digital libraries and COVID-19: responding to a global emergency. 2020;1–2.

6. Bond University Library (<https://library.bond.edu.au>) (/) 1. 2020;1–5.

7. Heckel J. Survey of U.S academic libraries documents COVID-19 pandemic responses. *Phys Org* [Internet]. 2020;1–3. Available from: <https://phys.org/news/2020-03-survey-academic-libraries-documents-covid-.html>

8. Questions G. COVID - 19 FAQ for Library Services. 2020;1–3.

9. Sucharita Publicatoin V. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research. *Int J Multidiscip Educ Res* [Internet]. 2020;1(3):427–46. Available from: http://ijee.ieefoundation.org/vol2/public_html/ijeeindex/vol2/issue4/IJEE_03_v2n4.pdf

10. Brown S, Clark L, Houser S, Kilby C, Lyle A, Mackinney L, et al. Recommendations for Library Services During The Covid-19 Pandemic Regents Public Library Advisory Council (RPLAC). 2020;(April):14. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/downloads/community-mitigation-strategy.pdf>

11. Brown WK. Libraries Adapt amid Crisis | American Libraries Magazine. 2020;(May). Available from: <https://americanlibrariesmagazine.org/2020/05/01/libraries-adapt-amid-crisis/>

12. Ali MY, Gatiti P. The COVID-19 (Coronavirus) pandemic: reflections on the roles of librarians and information professionals. *Health Info Libr J*. 2020;37(2):158–62.

13. D. Mestri D. Reopening libraries in COVID 19 pandemic: challenges and recommendations. *IP Indian J Libr Sci Inf Technol*. 2020;5(1):16–23.

14. June U. Library Services and Resources During Coronavirus Response See Our FAQ on Resuming Library Services What 's changed as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic ? 2020;1–2.

15. Hameed, A. B. Students perception and utilization of serial materials in the Polytechnic Ibadan Library, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education and Society*, 1(2) 3.

16. Gama, U. G. 2013. “Reference Services in the Digital Age: What hope for reference librarians in Nigeria” *Journal of Library and Information Sciences*, 2010;1 (1), 32-39.

17. Nwalo, K. I.N. *Fundamentals of library practice: A manual on library routines*. Ibadan: Sterling-Horden Publishers Ltd.2003

18Hisle, W. L. Top issues facing academic libraries: a report of the focus on the future task force. *College and Research Library News*, 2005;63(10):714717. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4765&context=libphilprac>